

FOREIGN EXPERIENCES OF ETHNO-CULTURAL TOURISM

T.Safarova

associate professor of the Department of Social Sciences

Tashkent Financial Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10430717>

Based on forecasts for the next few years, tourism will develop more and more rapidly in the world. Tourist flows will grow in all directions, both internationally and domestically. The most characteristic trends of tourism development in the current period include the increase of tourist destinations and the expansion of the type of tourist products.

Types of tourism such as extreme tourism, ecotourism, agrotourism, etc. are becoming more and more popular. Any type of tourism, in particular, is a form of interethnic relations, so almost every type of tourism includes an element of ethnocultural tourism. UN World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) according to the data, in 2019, Uzbekistan took one of the lowest places in the ranking of the most visited countries in the world. Various factors affect the expansion and decrease of tourist arrivals in different countries.

For example, UNWTO According to estimates, France is the first (86.3 million), followed by the United States (77.9 million), Spain (68.1 million), China (56.9 million) and Italy (50.8 million).

Considerable experience has also been accumulated in the organization of ethnocultural tourism abroad, and its study is especially important for Uzbekistan, as these experiences contribute to the search for alternative solutions in the organization of this type of tourism.¹ Australia, Canada, Nepal, Ecuador and other countries can be highlighted among the leading countries in ethno-cultural tourism, and this can be considered in a few examples.

Ecuador is located in two hemispheres of the Earth and is a country with the most dramatic climate differences on the planet. Isolation from the outside world created a unique basis for the development of ethno-cultural tourism here. Ecuador travel guides have information on more than 40 travel agencies that offer family-friendly ethnocultural tours, rainforest trekking and local culture.

These tourism community enterprises were created with the support of local organizations, local environmental protection funds and a number of travel

¹ Safarova, T. R. (2023). IMPROVING AND MODERNIZING THE SYSTEM OF STAFF TRAINING IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM. ONLINE SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT ANALYSIS, 3(11), 124-128.

agencies.² These companies are run by local groups of people who control hunting and create protected natural areas on Indian lands where hunting and farming are prohibited. In the early 1980s, the economic crisis forced the local population to look for additional livelihood activities: collecting and selling medicinal plants, selling forest trees and other products. But all these options did not meet the criteria of environmental sustainability and required their abandonment. The only promising initiative was the development of ethnocultural tourism.

Local residents have started organizing canoe tours for amateur tourists traveling in the form of ethno-cultural tourism. First of all, it was clear that the cultural features of the local population are of interest to the guests no less than the natural environment, therefore special attention was paid to the ethnocultural aspects in the planning of excursions. Gradually, the volume of tourism increased, the infrastructure developed: there was simple housing for tourists, as well as small ethnomuseums.

References:

1. Safarova, T. R. (2023). IMPROVING AND MODERNIZING THE SYSTEM OF STAFF TRAINING IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM. ONLINE SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT ANALYSIS, 3(11), 124-128.
2. Rustamkulovna, ST (2023). ALWAYS WALK POSITIVE AND BEAUTIFUL (THE SPIRITUAL AND ETHICAL DOCTRINE OF THE EAST IN TOURISM). ONLINE SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT ANALYSIS, 3(5), 464-466.
3. Safarova, TR (2022). Main Directions for Improving International Tourism Statistics. Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities, 13, 20-22.
4. Safarova, T. R. (2023). IMPROVING AND MODERNIZING THE SYSTEM OF STAFF TRAINING IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM. ONLINE SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT ANALYSIS, 3(11), 124-128.

² Rustamkulovna, ST (2023). ALWAYS WALK POSITIVE AND BEAUTIFUL (THE SPIRITUAL AND ETHICAL DOCTRINE OF THE EAST IN TOURISM). ONLINE SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT ANALYSIS, 3(5), 464-466.

